

APPLICATION OF MIXTURE LAW TO RHEOCHOR. PART I

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Mixture law has been applied to rheochor and mixtures of associated solutes in associated solvents have been studied. The values of R_x for acetone in acetic acid show a close agreement with R_{obs} observed, while in methyl alcohol and ethyl alcohol the straight line mixture law seems to hold. The agreement between R_x and R_{obs} for acetic acid is better in EtOH than in MeOH. The results for MeOH in ethyl alcohol also show that the mixture law is applicable. For the same solutes, the agreement between R_x and R_{obs} in different associated solvents is in the order: acetic acid > EtOH > MeOH. With increase of temperature, the values of R_x and R_{obs} fall and approach the R_{calc} , as it is the value at the boiling point of the liquid.

Friend (*Nature*, 1942, **140**, 432) suggested that in Sugden's parachor $\sigma \frac{1}{2}$ may be substituted by $\eta \frac{1}{2}$, where σ and η are the surface tension and viscosity respectively of the liquid. This gives

$$\frac{M\eta^{\frac{1}{2}}}{D} = \text{Constant} = R$$

where M is the molecular weight and D , the density of the liquid. The name 'Rheochor' was suggested for this constant. Friend (*loc. cit.*) observe that isomerides yield identical values of R . Bhagwat, Toshniwal and Moghe (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1944, **21**, 29) and Friend and Hargreaves (*Phil. Mag.*, 1943, *vii*, **34**, 643, 810; 1944, **35**, 57, 136, 619) have determined the values of atomic rheochor. Following are the values:—

C	... 12.8	Cl	... 27.3	N (-)	... 6.6
H in (C-H)	... 5.5	NH ₂	... 20.6		... 9.7
H in (O-H)	... 10.0	C ₆ H ₅ attached to alkyls	100.7	Br	... 36.0
O< (etheric)	... 10.0	, attached to other groups	102.7	(CO. acids and esters)	... 36.0
O= (ketonic)	... 13.2	Saturated six mem- bered carbon ring	-5.6		
Co-valent bond	... 0.0	CN	... 33.0		
Co-ordinate bond	... -0.1	NH	... 13.6		

Bhagwat *et al.* (*loc. cit.*) tried to apply mixture law to rheochor. From the results (given in Chemists Year Book, 1937) they have shown that the law is applicable to sugar solutions. The work was extended by Bhagwat and Maudloi (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1946, **23**, 349) but no systematic work seems to have been done on these lines. Hammic and Andrew (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 754) have studied the application of mixture law to parachor. They have divided liquid mixtures into following groups: (i) Non-associated solutes in non-associated solvents, (ii) associated solutes in non-associated solvents and (iii) associated liquids in associated solvents. In all these cases they observed that for all concentrations of the solute the mixture law was applicable, but in all these cases the surface tensions of the

component liquids did not differ by more than 7 dynes/cm. For other liquid mixtures, where the difference was greater, the straight line mixture law was found to be applicable.

No results are given for water as a solvent, although they have concluded that the behaviour is anomalous. In the light of these observations for liquid-liquid mixtures in determining parachor, we thought it advisable to study the application of mixture law to rheochor on the same lines. Our results are given in the following pages.

EXPERIMENTAL

Viscosity of liquids and their mixtures was determined with the help of Ostwald's viscometer. Same viscometer and the same volume of liquids were used. The time for the flow of the liquid between two marks was noted by a stop-watch. The temperature was maintained constant between the limits $\pm 0.1^\circ$ by immersing the viscometer and the pyknometer in a thermostat regulated by electrical thermo-regulator. The density of the liquid or the mixture was determined with the help of a pyknometer. All the liquids used were 'A.R.' B.D.H. samples or Merck's samples and were distilled before use. If η_1 and η_2 are the viscosities of the liquid and the water respectively, d_1 and d_2 , their densities, and t_1 and t_2 , the time of fall between two marks, then $\eta_2/\eta_1 = d_2 t_2 / d_1 t_1$; the viscosity of water at a particular temperature is obtained from the standard tables and hence η_2 is calculated. The value so obtained is substituted in the expression

$$R = \frac{M(10^3\eta)^{\frac{1}{3}}}{D + 2d}$$

As η is very small, $10^3\eta$ is used. Further, d , the density of the substance in vapour state is very small. Hence the expression

$$R = \frac{M(10^3\eta)^{\frac{1}{3}}}{D} \text{ is used. For liquid mixtures}$$

$$R_m = \frac{M_m(10^3\eta)^{\frac{1}{3}}}{D}$$

where $M_m = (1-x)M + xM_x$ and $R_m = (1-x)R + xR_x$; M_m = mean molecular weight of the mixture, M = the molecular weight of the solvent, M_x = the molecular weight of the solute, R_m = the rheochor of the mixture, R = the rheochor of the solvent, R_x = the rheochor of the solute and x is the molar fraction of the solute in $(1-x)$ molecules of the solvent.

The liquids chosen were miscible in all proportions and hence the molar fraction of the solute was changed from 0 to 1. The results of viscosities obtained for standard liquids by the authors and those given in standard tables at the same temperature did not always agree, but since the same apparatus and liquids were used all throughout and that for establishing mixture law, comparison of experimental results alone was necessary; the point of identity between the results given in standard tables and those obtained by the authors was not much stressed. Further, in the expression $\eta^{\frac{1}{3}}$ is used so that even as high an error as 8% in η becomes only 1% in $\eta^{\frac{1}{3}}$.

Associated Liquids in Associated Solvents

TABLE I

Methyl alcohol in ethyl alcohol.

Temp. = 30°.

x .	D .	$\eta \times 10^3$.	M_m .	R_m .	R_x .
0.000	0.7914	9.98	46.0	77.50	—
0.1388	0.7921	9.26	44.00	73.46	48.50
0.2516	0.7914	8.64	42.43	71.21	48.40
0.4752	0.7936	7.87	41.19	67.50	49.22
0.5797	0.7956	7.23	38.01	61.17	48.80
0.6891	0.7921	6.74	36.35	56.25	50.35
0.8384	0.7914	6.10	34.20	54.25	49.72
0.9272	0.7943	5.77	33.02	51.60	49.72
1.000	0.7969	5.60	32.0	—	—

 R_{calc} for methyl alcohol = 49.3 ; R_{obs} = 49.72.

The values of R_x shows that the mixture law is applicable, although at smaller concentrations of methyl alcohol the values are somewhat lower. No regular change is observed as the concentration is increased and the deviation from the observed value for pure methyl alcohol is within the experimental limits, since R_x is calculated from the mixture law,

$$R_m = (1-x)R + xR_x$$

and the error becomes more magnified, the smaller the value of x .

TABLE II

Acetic acid in ethyl alcohol.

Temp. = 30°.

x .	D .	$\eta \times 10^3$.	M_m .	R_m .	R_x .
0.0	0.7989	10.14	46.00	77.69	—
0.1290	0.8260	10.56	47.80	77.69	77.96
0.1603	0.8335	10.67	48.27	77.78	78.00
0.3391	0.8820	11.34	50.75	77.93	78.50
0.5555	0.8399	12.09	53.78	78.12	78.50
0.7714	0.9926	12.26	56.80	78.25	78.45
0.8364	1.1009	11.99	57.73	78.21	78.30
1.0000	1.1040	10.52	60.00	—	77.47

 R_{calc} for acetic acid = 75.3 ; R_{obs} = 77.47.

Temp. = 40°.

0.0000	0.7859	8.07	46.00	76.0	—
0.1290	0.8219	8.69	47.80	76.2	77.59
0.1603	0.8303	8.79	48.27	76.28	77.02
0.3391	0.8764	9.27	50.25	76.49	77.45
0.5555	0.9322	10.16	53.78	77.00	77.78
0.7714	0.9860	10.15	56.80	76.96	77.25
0.8364	1.1000	9.42	57.73	76.82	76.96
1.0000	1.1036	9.07	60.00	—	76.32

 R_{obs} = 76.32.

TABLE II (contd.)

Temp. = 50°.

x .	D .	$\eta \times 10^3$.	M_m .	R_m .	R_x .
0.0000	0.7877	7.04	46.00	74.54	—
0.1290	0.8172	7.24	47.80	74.86	—
0.1603	0.8273	7.29	48.27	74.74	77.03
0.3391	0.8724	7.76	50.75	75.15	75.65
0.5555	0.9307	8.27	53.78	75.26	76.35
0.7714	0.9824	8.51	56.80	75.37	75.24
0.8364	0.9997	8.41	57.73	75.35	75.61
1.0000	1.1034	7.82	60.00	—	75.50
					75.08

 $R_{obs} = 75.18$.

TABLE III

Acetic acid in methyl alcohol.

Temp. = 30°.

x .	D .	$\eta \times 10^3$.	M_m .	R_m .	R_x .
0.0000	0.7969	5.60	32.00	19.72	—
0.2445	0.8828	7.55	38.84	36.78	78.57
0.4145	0.9330	8.83	43.61	61.37	77.84
0.6115	0.9779	11.08	49.12	67.84	79.38
0.7998	1.1015	11.68	54.39	72.85	78.56
1.0000	1.1040	10.55	60.00	—	77.47

Temp. = 40°.

x .	D .	$\eta \times 10^3$.	M_m .	R_m .	R_x .
0.0000	0.7912	1.10	32.00	18.60	—
0.2445	0.8758	6.30	38.84	35.76	77.93
0.4145	0.9266	7.59	43.61	60.49	77.28
0.6115	0.9705	9.16	49.12	66.76	78.27
0.7998	1.1008	9.68	54.39	71.63	77.39
1.0000	1.1036	9.07	60.00	—	76.32

Temp. = 50°.

x .	D .	$\eta \times 10^3$.	M_m .	R_m .	R_x .
0.0000	0.7880	3.99	32.00	47.97	—
0.2445	0.8694	5.48	38.84	55.26	77.84
0.4145	0.9215	6.62	43.61	59.94	76.86
0.6115	0.9620	7.76	49.12	65.97	77.43
0.7998	1.1003	8.20	54.39	70.50	76.14
1.0000	1.1034	7.82	60.00	—	75.08

TABLE IV

Acetone in acetic acid.

Temp. = 30°.

x .	D .	$\eta \times 10^3$.	M_m .	R_m .	R_x .
0.0000	1.0410	10.730	60.0000	77.52	—
0.1977	0.9771	8.794	59.6186	79.25	86.62
0.3556	0.9410	7.338	59.2888	80.81	86.81
0.4737	0.9120	6.132	59.0526	81.23	85.98
0.6327	0.8707	5.055	58.7346	82.58	85.52
0.6336	0.8707	5.049	58.7328	82.58	85.49
0.8750	0.8111	3.862	58.2500	85.12	86.09
1.0000	0.7811	3.419	58.0000	—	86.56

 R_{calc} for acetone = 84.6; R_{obs} = 86.56.

TABLE IV (contd.)

Temp. = 40°.					
x_a	$D.$	$\eta \times 10^3$	$M_m.$	$R_m.$	$R_x.$
0.0000	1.0298	9.082	60.0000	76.83	—
0.1907	0.9771	7.501	59.6186	78.46	85.42
0.3556	0.9293	6.209	59.2888	80.15	85.22
0.4737	0.9016	5.426	59.0526	80.92	85.47
0.6327	0.8509	4.526	58.7343	82.35	85.53
0.6336	0.8609	4.508	58.7328	82.33	85.49
0.8750	0.8007	3.595	58.2500	85.00	86.27
1.0000	0.7705	3.116	58.0000	—	86.76

 $R_{obs} = 86.76$

Temp. = 50°.

0.0000	1.0183	7.785	60.0000	76.19	—
0.1907	0.9663	6.839	59.6186	78.43	87.93
0.3556	0.9183	5.461	59.2888	79.82	86.38
0.4737	0.8909	4.829	59.0526	80.69	85.68
0.6327	0.8497	4.070	58.7346	82.35	85.91
0.6336	0.8497	4.070	58.7328	82.35	85.90
0.8750	0.7889	3.212	58.2500	85.43	86.75
1.0000	0.7587	2.859	58.0000	—	87.16

 $R_{obs} = 86.76.$

TABLE V

Acetone in methyl alcohol.

Temp. = 30°.

x_a	$D.$	$\eta \times 10^3$	$M_m.$	$R_m.$	$R_x.$
0.0000	0.7921	5.745	32.0000	50.25	—
0.1135	0.7936	4.998	34.9510	53.34	82.02
0.1964	0.7932	4.750	37.1064	55.43	81.77
0.4456	0.7921	3.915	43.5856	65.25	83.90
0.6076	0.7889	3.667	47.7876	71.24	84.79
0.7939	0.7862	3.477	52.6414	78.23	85.50
0.9136	0.7838	3.426	55.9536	83.26	86.38
1.0000	0.7811	3.394	58.0000	—	86.48

Temp. = 40°.

0.0070	0.7839	5.148	32.0000	50.08	—
0.1135	0.7844	4.552	34.9510	53.84	83.23
0.1964	0.7825	4.227	37.1064	56.76	84.11
0.4456	0.7829	3.627	43.5856	65.39	84.44
0.6076	0.7785	3.419	47.7876	71.55	85.41
0.7939	0.7750	3.179	52.6414	78.42	85.81
0.9136	0.7719	3.108	55.9536	83.51	86.57
1.0000	0.7705	3.082	58.0000	—	86.64

Temp. = 50°.

0.0000	0.7750	4.327	32.0000	49.69	—
0.1135	0.7754	3.869	34.9510	53.37	82.20
0.1964	0.7723	3.620	37.1064	56.43	84.01
0.4556	0.7682	3.154	43.5856	65.48	85.12
0.6076	0.7672	3.004	47.7876	71.45	85.50
0.7939	0.7638	2.888	52.6414	78.66	86.18
0.9136	0.7609	2.810	55.9536	83.66	87.97
1.0000	0.7587	2.803	58.0000	—	86.94

TABLE VI
Acetone in ethyl alcohol.

Temp. = 30°.					
x .	D .	$\eta \times 10^3$.	M_{12} .	R_m .	R_x .
0.0000	0.7919	10.610	46.0000	78.05	—
0.1622	0.7909	7.565	47.9464	78.23	79.16
0.2894	0.7895	5.917	49.4728	78.23	78.64
0.6712	0.7848	3.931	54.0544	81.36	82.98
0.7382	0.7842	3.794	54.8584	82.62	84.24
0.8267	0.7840	3.775	55.9204	84.22	85.50
1.0000	0.7811	3.360	58.0000	—	86.38
Temp. = 40°.					
0.0000	0.7827	8.414	46.0000	76.70	—
0.1622	0.7825	6.316	47.9464	77.13	79.40
0.2894	0.7803	5.089	49.4728	77.67	80.09
0.6712	0.7756	3.565	54.0544	81.70	84.13
0.7382	0.7750	3.452	54.8584	82.62	84.73
0.8267	0.7737	3.297	55.9204	83.89	85.39
1.0000	0.7713	3.137	58.0000	—	86.72
Temp. = 50°.					
0.0000	0.7746	6.993	46.0000	75.39	—
0.1622	0.7740	5.335	47.9464	76.37	81.44
0.2894	0.7705	4.398	49.4728	77.25	81.78
0.6712	0.7633	3.213	54.0544	81.93	85.13
0.7382	0.7615	3.103	54.8584	82.96	85.62
0.8267	0.7597	2.942	55.9204	84.24	86.10
1.0000	0.7578	2.840	58.0000	—	87.18

The values of R_x for acetic acid in ethyl alcohol at all temperatures show a close agreement with R_{obs} for acetic acid at the corresponding temperatures. The value of R_x falls with temperature, so also the value of R_{obs} and both show better agreement with the calculated values at higher temperatures. This is as is expected, since R_{calc} always corresponds to the boiling point temperature of the liquid. The values of R_x for acetic acid in methyl alcohol show a similar behaviour.

The results with acetone in acetic acid show a close agreement between R_{obs} and R_{calc} for all concentrations. R_{obs} at different temperatures examined by us does not show much variation with temperature, since the temperatures examined are not far removed from the boiling point of acetone.

In the cases of methyl alcohol and ethyl alcohol, as solvents for acetone, the R_{obs} and R_x do not agree at all concentrations. The values which are low at lower concentrations increase steadily with increase in the concentration of acetone. In short, it seems that the straight line mixture law is applicable.